

Science technology & Digital finance

journal homepage: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf>

EVENT TOURISM CENTERS OF SPAIN

Sirlibekov Khabibullo Shakarboy ugli

Trainee teacher of the Department of Economics and tourism of the Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek.

ЦЕНТРЫ СОБЫТИЙНОГО ТУРИЗМА ИСПАНИИ

Сирлибеков Хабибулло Шакарбой угли

Преподаватель-стажер кафедры экономики и туризма Джизакского филиала Национального университета Узбекистана имени Мирзо Улугбека.

ISPANIYANING TADBIR TURIZM MARKAZLARI

Sirlibekov Xabibullo Shakarboy o'g'li

Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali Iqtisodiyot va turizm kafedrasida stajyor o'qituvchisi.

abstract

This article is devoted to the main features of event tourism and its centers in the Kingdom of Spain. The article attempts to define the essence of event tourism as a special type of tourism activity, identify motives for visiting cultural attractions and activities while traveling as well as discover the main tourist centers related to this type of tourism in Spain. Based on the article, conclusions were drawn about the most popular destinations for event tourism in Spain.

аннотация

Настоящая статья посвящена основным особенностям событийного туризма и его центрам в Королевстве Испания. В статье предпринята попытка определения сущности событийного туризма, как особого вида туристической деятельности, выявления мотивов посещения культурных достопримечательностей и мероприятий во время путешествий, а также выделения основных туристических центров, относящихся к данному виду туризма на территории Испании. На основе статьи были сделаны выводы о наиболее популярных направлениях в рамках событийного туризма в Испании.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola Ispaniya Qirolligidagi voqealar turizmi va uning markazlari asosiy xususiyatlarga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada voqealar turizmining mohiyatini quyidagicha aniqlashga harakat qilindi turistik faoliyatning maxsus turi, tashrif sabablarini aniqlash sayohat paytida madaniy diqqatga sazovor joylar va tadbirlar va shuningdek, ushbu markazga tegishli asosiy sayyohlik markazlarining ajratilishi Ispaniya hududida turizm turi. Maqola asosida Ispaniyadagi voqealar turizmi doirasidagi eng mashhur yo'nalishlar haqida xulosalar chiqarildi.

Keywords:

event tourism, Spain, tourist center, tourist destination, events.

Ключевые слова:

событийный туризм, Испания, туристический центр, туристское направление, события.

Kalit so'zlar:

voqea turizmi, Ispaniya, sayyohlik markazi, turistik joy, tadbirlar.

© 2023 *Sirlibekov Khabibullo Shakarboy ugli.*

Event tourism is a special area of development of the tourism services market. Recently, event tourism has become increasingly popular on the world market due to the fact that tourists increasingly prefer, spending their leisure time in areas with unique historical, cultural or natural conditions, to diversify it with various events held as part of the trip.

Humanity has always shown, shows and will continue to show interest in the traditions and culture of other peoples, even despite various obstacles, such as the unfavorable epidemiological situation and the closure of borders.

Although the Spanish event tourism industry is still relatively young and in its infancy, it faces the same difficulties as the global event tourism industry as a whole. Therefore the main problem at the present stage of the development of event tourism is the provision of social and cultural services of appropriate quality to tourists, which does not always work out.

The works of such scientists as Alexandrova A.Yu., Duel A., Babkin A.V. and others, who contributed to the study of this phenomenon, are of great importance for the development of event tourism. Event tourism as one of the types of tourist activity is devoted to more than one study, for example, the work of O.V. Alekseeva [2].

The purpose of the study is to analyze the phenomenon of event tourism in Spain in the past and in identifying the prospects for its development in the future. Spain was chosen as the object of research not by chance, as this country offers tourists the opportunity not only to have a good rest, but also to enrich their personal views on Southwestern Europe with new impressions and knowledge and expand their own horizons. Every year Spain is visited by a huge number of tourists, as the country has a lot of completely different tourist resources for every taste and budget.

However, it turns out that tourists are beginning to make higher and higher demands. requirements for tourist products. Thus, the trip, which includes not only visiting the most famous cities of Spain, but also celebrating world holidays such as Christmas and New Year, medical and wellness holidays, as well as local traditional holidays and rituals, will be in great demand in the tourist market. Studying various literary sources that consider the development of Spanish event tourism, we can conclude that this direction of tourism is constantly developing, largely following the established world traditions.

Therefore, the main problem at the present stage of the development of event tourism is the provision of proper quality services to event tourists. An event tour is a journey dedicated to large—scale events and bright events that combines recreation and participation in traditional festivals, fairs and rituals. Spain has a huge cultural and

historical heritage, and thanks to them and rich folklore traditions Spain is in the top of the most popular countries for tourism. Exciting traditional celebrations: Fallas in Valencia, San Fermin in Pamplona, the April Fair in Seville, La Tomatina in Bunyola, the second largest carnival in the world in Tenerife, Formula 1 stages in three cities Spain (Barcelona, Jerez de la Frontera, Valencia), a real traditional bullfight, football matches with the participation of legendary Real teams

Madrid and Barcelona, a huge variety of religious, folk festivals and food festivals throughout the country. Spain is perfect a place to escape from everyday routine and the dullness of everyday life and plunge into a great variety of colors, sounds, tastes and emotions propose to consider some of the main centers of event tourism, which open up to visitors the most colorful and complete picture of Spanish culture. First of all, I would like to highlight the carnival, which is held annually in February throughout Spain. In each city, the carnival is held in different ways, with its own distinctive features and peculiarities. However, the most magnificent celebration takes place in Barcelona, Cadiz and Tenerife. It is there that you should go in order to get acquainted with this amazing event.

The carnival lasts about 1-2 weeks and has a program of events that is different in each city. It includes events such as the sardine funeral, a ritual in which people burn an effigy of sardines; it marks the beginning of Lent, Taronhada, which is also called the orange Battle. Previously, under Catalonia, the carnival ended with her. The fighting was especially fierce during the years of a good harvest of oranges. For some time now people they began to treat oranges more economically and replaced them with orange balls, candy wrappers and confetti. A special place in the implementation of event tourism in Spain is played by La Tomatina is an annual celebration held in Bunyola, Valencia, in the last week of August. Thousands of participants from different countries take part in a battle in which tomatoes are used as weapons. According to the data provided by the media, 20,000 tourists from all over the world visited the holiday in 2018. A total of 145 tons of tomatoes were harvested for the battle It is also impossible not to celebrate the feast of the Three Magi, which is traditionally celebrated on January 6. It is believed that on this day the Eastern sages visited Bethlehem to worship the newborn Jesus and bring him gold, frankincense and myrrh as a gift. That's why nowadays gifts are an important part of the era of Spanish magicians. We can definitely say that the day The Three Magi in Spain is one of the most important events of January, especially in Barcelona. Traditionally, on this day, pages and fairies distribute specially prepared sweet treats to people. In 2015, the participants of the parade in Barcelona 4.6 tons of sweets were distributed to the audience. Anyone between the ages of 8 and 99 can take part in the celebration. To do this, he needs to

fill out a special questionnaire on the organizer's website, get the necessary instructions and take part in rehearsals. The holiday includes a spectacular procession in which life-size dolls, acrobats, musicians, dancers etc. take part. Thus, Spain provides a huge choice in the field of event tourism. There everyone will be able to find what he likes and diversify your vacation by visiting a grand celebration. Spaniards are a very expressive people, this is reflected in their culture, holidays and traditions like nowhere else, so even the most sophisticated tourist will not suffer from a lack of emotions after visiting an event. MV Sokolova formulated the meaning and role of event tourism as follows: "One of the most important knowledge that tourists receive is tolerance, when the legitimacy of the "friend-or -foe" approach is rejected and the claims of one's own people are not accepted as the highest norm" [4]. In our opinion, Spain has endless development potential in this area. And event tourism in this country, as a special type of tourism activity, requires careful study and development of measures to promote it.

Reference:

1. Alexandrova, A.Yu. International tourism: Textbook/ A.Yu. Alexandrova. - M.: Aspect Press, 2004. - 470 p.
2. Alekseeva, O.V. Event tourism and event management //Russian entrepreneurship. 2011. No. 6. Issue. 2. pp. 167-172.
3. Babkin, A.V. Special types of tourism: studies. manual / A.V.Babkin. - Moscow: Soviet Sport, 2008. - 208 p. - ISBN 978-5-9718-0310-2. -Text: [electronic resource] // EBS "Student consultant". – Access mode:<https://www.studentlibrary.ru/book/ISBN9785971803102.html> (date of application:10/15/2022).
4. Bulganina S.V., Lopatkina N.S. Event tourism: history andprospects of development // Online journal "SCIENCE Studies" Volume 7, No3(2015). – Access mode: <http://naukovedenie.ru/PDF/168EVN315.pdf> . Cover from thescreen. Yaz. rus, Eng. DOI: 10.15862/168EVN315 (accessed: 15.01.2021).
5. Voronkova, L.P. History of tourism and hospitality: educationalmanual / Voronkova L.P. — Moscow: KnoRus, 2020. — 347 p. <https://www.book.ru/book/932541> (accessed: 10/15/2022).
6. Sokolova, M.V. Tourism as a cultural phenomenon: morphological aspect
7. // Modern problems of service and tourism (electronic journal). 2014. Vol. 8.No. 4. pp. 55-67. DOI: 10.12737/6575. – Access mode:http://spstjournal.org/Archive_article/2014/2014_04/02-Sokolova.pdf (accessed: 10/15/2022).
8. Botir M. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O ‘TISH DAVRIDA YUZAGA KELAYOTGAN MUAMMOLAR //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – C. 257-260.
9. Mukhtorov B., Ermatov M. METHODS OF EFFECTIVE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT //International Journal Of Management And Economics Fundamental. – 2023. – T. 3. – №. 05. – C. 76-80.
10. Мухтаров Б., Хайруллаев Н. Преимущества и недостатки оффшорных зон //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.

11. Цой М. П., Эшонкулов Т., Касимова Д. П. Реформы в сфере образования Республики Узбекистан //Гуманитарные науки в XXI веке. – 2014. – №. 18. – С. 210-213.
12. Цой М. П., Худояров Р. Т. МАЛЫЙ И СРЕДНИЙ БИЗНЕС В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ МИРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 132-136.
13. Shahzod M. O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 153-156.
14. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. Big data types of education system and opportunities for using them in the field //journal of academic research and trends in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
15. Xudoyorov R. COMPILATION OF FINANCIAL REPORTS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 175-186.
16. Usmanova V. INCREASING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 131-138.
17. Yusufjon A. DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 03. – С. 5-8.
18. Abror R., Shahobiddin K. INNOVATIVE MARKETING AND ITS DEVELOPMENT //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 193-196.
19. Rashidov A., Leonodovna M. N., Azlarkhan A. The importance of financial accounting in business decision-making //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2023. – Т. 21. – С. 1-4.
20. Sardor B., Ibragimovich T. K. Digital Transformation Directions in the Restaurant Business //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 1-4.
21. Bo'ltakov S. et al. TURIZM SOHASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI AHAMIYATI //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 60-62.
22. Raipovna V. S., Akramovich N. A., Sevinch K. PRODUCTION CAPACITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND WAYS TO INCREASE IT //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 238-241.
23. Holmuradovich X. B. et al. THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPORTS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN, THE GUARANTEE OF THE HEALTHY AND WELL-ROUNDED YOUTH //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 266-269.
24. Holmuradovich X. B. et al. GOVERNMENT AND NON-GOVERNMENT FORMS OF BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP SUPPORT //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 258-265.
25. Худояров Р., Низаметдинов А. МАЛЫЙ И СРЕДНИЙ БИЗНЕС В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ МИРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6 Part 2. – С. 188-193.
26. Туйчиева Н. Elektron Ta 'lim Tizimining Afzalliklari Va Kamchiliklari //Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 40-41.

27. Норбеков Х. Методики анализа и оценка взаимный преимуществ предприятия //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2022.
28. Bahrom X. et al. O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSHNING IQTISODIY MUNOSABATLARI //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – С. 63-69.
29. Sarvar G., Sirojiddin S. Pulatova Mashhura Xushnodbek qizi.(2022). Factors affecting labor relations and its wage //Journal of academic research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 125-129.
30. Akramovich N. A., Sarvar G., Yassim H. THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 95-99.
31. G'Aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. O 'zbekistonda iste'mol savatchasi hozirgi holatini va uni shakillantirish yo 'nalishlari //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 119-125.
32. O'G'Li N. D. R., Qizi T. D. Z. MOLIYA BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA UNGA OID YANGI YONDASHUVLAR //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 1-4.
33. Najmiddinov D. R., Shodlikov D. E. THE EFFECT OF THE SECRET ECONOMY IN A DAILY LIFE OF THE SOCIETY //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1A. – С. 56-59.
34. Uchkun S., Dilshod N. PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING THE SIGNIFICANT ACCOUNTS IN THE REVENUE CYCLE //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 32-36.
35. Alijon N., Sirojiddin S., Azizbek A. FRANCHISE SYSTEM IN BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 250-257.
36. Sarvar G. et al. FACTORS AFFECTING LABOR RELATIONS AND ITS WAGE //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 125-129.
37. Sirojiddin S. et al. PRICE AND ITS ROLE IN ENSURING THE STABILITY OF PRODUCTS AND RAW MATERIALS IN SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 357-365.
38. Соловарова М. А. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СЕТИ ОТЕЛЕЙ MARRIOTT //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 98-103.
39. Наркузиев А. Р. ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПОНЯТИЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ КАК ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ КАТЕГОРИИ И ЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В СФЕРЕ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА //PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 21. – С. 11-14.
40. Narkuziyev A. R. ICHKI RESURSLARGA ASOSLANGAN HUDUDIY INFRATUZILMANI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASINI QO 'LLASH (O 'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SOHASI UCHUN FOYDALANISH IMKOMIYATLARI) //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. TSTU Conference 2. – С. 390-400.
41. Sirlibekov, K. (2023). PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(3), 123-131. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/xss>

42. Kamolov D. R. O. G. L. O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – C. 348-352.
43. Kamolov Dostonbek, “SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY”, *SSAI*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 128–133, Oct. 2023, Accessed: Nov. 07, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/ssai/article/view/89>
44. Kamolov D. Davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar //Адабиёт учкунлари. – 2021.
45. Kamolov, Dostonbek. (2023). ON THE WAY TO THE DIGITAL EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN. 10.13140/RG.2.2.11566.18242.
46. Kamolov, Dostonbek. (2022). DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQ : GENEZISI VA ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI. 10.13140/RG.2.2.24017.61285.
47. Aliqulov, B. (2023). THE HISTORY OF THE URBAN PLANNING CULTURE OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE ROLE OF THE AFROSIAB MONUMENT IN ITS STUDY. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 116-119. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/baa>
48. Boltakov, S., & Akhrorov, S. (2023). APPEARANCE AND FEATURES OF MONEY. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 97-101. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/bsas>
49. Khidirnazarov, A. (2023). DEVELOPMENT TREND AND FORECAST OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN (On the example of the analysis of 2022 and the forecast for 2023-2024). *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 79-90. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/kha>
50. Bultakov, S., & Bozorboyev, D. (2023). THE MEANING AND ESSENCE OF THE LEGISLATION ON THE EMERGENCE AND COMPETITION OF THE COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT IN UZBEKISTAN. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 73-78. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/dbsb>
51. Boltakov, S. (2023). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DIGITIZATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES. *Science technology&Digital Finance*, 1(4), 10-20. <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/stdf/article/view/bsa>

SUPPORT RESULT
JOURNALS